

SPATIO-TEMPORAL INVESTIGATION OF VEGETATION DYNAMICS AND ITS EFFECTS ON CLIMATIC VARIABILITY IN TANGAZA, SOKOTO STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Vegetation dynamics has significant impacts on climatic variability by influencing factors like surface temperature, precipitation patterns, and the water cycle. As vegetation changes, it can alter local and regional climates, for example, the albedo effect phenomenon and evapotranspiration. However, the impact of vegetation changes in relation to desert encroachment as an environmental challenge in Tangaza, Sokoto State, has not been investigated, constituting a research gap. Tangaza, in Sokoto State, Nigeria, is one of the locations experiencing desertification. The presence of sand dunes in Tangaza provides physical evidence of desert encroachment with impacts such as land degradation and reduced crop yield. This study investigates how changes in vegetation dynamics influence climatic variability in Tangaza. Using Landsat 8 Operational Land Imager and Digital Elevation Model (DEM) data, the research evaluates vegetation dynamics via Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) values for dry and rainy seasons across 2013 and 2018. It explores the relationship between stream order and vegetation density, revealing how hydrological features influence vegetation patterns. Key findings indicate that rainy seasons exhibit higher NDVI values due to increased rainfall, while the dry season shows vegetation decline, particularly near lower-order streams. For 2013, NDVI values for sparse vegetation increased by 17% between dry and rainy seasons (-0.275 – 0.06 and 0.063 – 0.170) respectively. For 2018, NDVI values for low vegetation increased by 4% only, between dry and rainy seasons (-0.219 – 0.095 and -0.146 – 0.173) respectively. These insights underscore the role of sustainable land management in mitigating vegetation loss, controlling desert encroachment, and promoting ecological resilience.

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INTRODUCTION

Desertification is considered one of the biggest threats facing the environment at the global level (United Nations Convention to Combat Desertification, 2013). It encompasses degradation of lands in arid, semi-arid, and dry sub-humid areas, resulting from a combination of climatic factors and human activity (UNCCD, 2013; Olagunju, 2015). This phenomenon, together with land degradation and drought, due to natural causes, human impact, or both, results in the erosion or reduction in value of natural capital, including land, water, and vegetation, which in turn affects human well-being. Land degradation reduces the productive capacity and value of soil, water, plant, and animal resources, while also diminishing ecosystem functions that support primary production and related economic activities. It further weakens ecosystem services and reduces biodiversity in both natural and human-modified environments, including agricultural lands, forests, and urban areas (UNCCD, 2013).

According to Article 1 of the United Nations Convention to Combat Desertification, land degradation is defined as the reduction or loss of biological or economic productivity and ecological complexity in rain-fed croplands, irrigated lands, rangelands, pastures, forests, and woodlands within arid, semi-arid, and dry sub-humid zones. This degradation results from land use practices or a combination of processes, including those driven by human activities and settlement patterns. Overall, desertification represents a progressive decline in land quality that threatens environmental sustainability, food security, and rural livelihoods worldwide.

- (i) Soil erosion caused by wind and/or water;
- (ii) Deterioration of the physical, chemical, and biological or economic properties of soil; and
- (iii) Long-term loss of natural vegetation.

Desertification is widely recognized as the intensification or expansion of desert-like conditions that results in a decline in biological productivity, including reduced plant biomass, decreased land carrying capacity for livestock, lower crop yields, and overall deterioration in human well-being (Jamala *et al.*; 2013). This knowledge points to the fact that desertification must be considered more as a process, and not as a state per se. The causes of its occurrence may be natural forces, humans or a combination of both, which makes its identification and assessment more complicated. Therefore, it is necessary to use time series data to record the changes in the environment over time, and not just use a single point or static data sets when considering desertification-affected areas.

Climatic variability is not the only one of the many human-induced factors that add to desertification. These include the harvesting of timber for timber production and hand fires where great amounts of carbon dioxide are released into the atmosphere as well as continual cultivation of "marginal" or "fragile" land. Fuelwood demand is still very high in areas like the Sahel Zone, caused by the high population growth and urbanisation. This has contributed to the surge in deforestation, and wood extraction for domestic fuel remains as one of the leading causes of loss of forests and the resultant land degradation (Jamala *et al.*, 2013).

Human activities continue to play major roles in desertification process, especially in Tangaza where human inappropriate uses of land and pressure are important drivers. Increased pressure on land resources in dryland areas due to rapid population growth, which exceeds the resources available on the land and creates demand for food, water, fuel, raw material and other goods and services. The traditional utilization of land especially related to nomadic pastoralism has been criticized for leading to degradation of the environment. Overgrazing happens when the number of animals reared is beyond the carrying capacity of the land reared, resulting in reduction of vegetation cover and soil nutrients (Olagunju, 2015). Likewise, when the fallow period is reduced or removed, the result is desertification because of nutrient depletion, loss of soil fertility and poor productivity.

Land degradation in dryland regions also is caused by mechanised agriculture. It is beneficial for large scale farming, but it reduces soil structure due to the heavy equipment and deep ploughing methods, increasing soil susceptibility to wind and water erosion (Jamala *et al.*, 2013). Furthermore, the bush burning to clear land, hunt or encourage pasture to grow further reduces vegetation and soil degradation. In many situations, the solution to the problem of insufficient or nonexistent fuelwood is to cut more trees than is healthy, especially in the poorest rural communities in the Sahel. These are all interrelated stresses and stresses that reflect the complexity of human causes of desertification, which are tightly connected to socio-economic disadvantage and resource dependence. Hence, vegetation dynamics are becoming a key component for the understanding and the management of land degradation processes in the degraded areas.

According to Ekpoh and Nsa (2011), vegetation cover is the percentage or proportion of an area covered by plant life. Contains diverse plant shapes including trees, shrubs, grasses, mosses, and ferns. Vegetation is all the plants living in an ecosystem and is vital to the ecological balance. It helps maintain biodiversity, habitat for wildlife, and is important in regulating ecological processes like nutrient cycling, carbon storage, and energy exchange. There is much variation in the kind of vegetation found in different parts of the environment depending on climate, soil characteristics, topography and disturbance history. Due to this, various ecological zones around the globe contain unique vegetation types such as tropical rainforest, savannah, desert, temperate forest, grassland, and tundra. This has resulted in a variety of ecological zones around the world with different vegetation types including tropical rainforest, savannah, desert, temperate forest, grassland and tundra regions (Ekpoh and Nsa, 2011; Olaniyi *et al.*, 2013).

Information on vegetation dynamics is important for assessing the health of an ecosystem, land use change, and the effects of human activities including urbanization, mining and agriculture. In addition, vegetation cover is an important environmental indicator used to assess the relationships between the land surface and climatic variables like temperature, precipitation, and evapotranspiration (ET) (Buba *et al.*, 2020). Additionally, vegetation has an important role in the local hydrological cycle and climate system, such as evapotranspiration, soil moisture retention, and soil stabilization (Ekpoh and Nsa, 2011). Numerous studies have also identified climate change as a key factor in influencing the variability of vegetation, and vegetation influences water, carbon and energy exchange between the land surface and the atmosphere (Olaniyi *et al.*, 2013; Jensen, 2015; Ibrahim *et al.*, 2017; Oluwaseyi, 2017; Agbaje *et al.*, 2020).

Vegetation changes are often variable in time and space and traditional methods of field monitoring are not always adequate for large-scale analysis. Consequently, remote sensing technologies have grown to be more significant in the past few decades for vegetation dynamic monitoring. These technologies deliver spatial and temporal data at a high level of resolution and in real time, enabling researchers to monitor vegetation changes across a wide geographic area (Agbaje *et al.*, 2020). The Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), Enhanced Vegetation Index (EVI) and Leaf Area Index (LAI) are three commonly used vegetation indices derived from satellite data. Of these, NDVI is considered one of the best indicators of vegetation health because of its high correlation with biomass and canopy cover as well as net primary productivity (Buba *et al.*, 2020).

Empirical research also has shown the value of using NDVI in the analysis of the environment. For instance, Griffith *et al.* (2002) analysed the link between NDVI, vegetation phenology and water quality parameters in Nebraska, Kansas and Missouri. They pointed out that when interpreting the vegetation indices, it was important to take into account the environmental conditions and land-use of the region in question. In a similar way, Sahu *et al.* (2024) used the morphometric indices derived from satellite data including NDVI, NDWI (Normalized Difference Water Index), and SAVI (Soil Adjusted Vegetation Index) to evaluate the vegetation, water and soil characteristics in the Palar River basin. They found high values at the correlation level between the morphometric parameters and the spectral indices, with groundwater data validation. Study has highlighted the need to incorporate the remote sensing data in drought mitigation measures and sustainable water resource management.

In general, the studies emphasize the need to consider desertification and vegetation as integrated environmental processes, influenced by both human activities and natural processes. The linkage between the vegetation cover and water availability has been studied by various researchers, many of whom have emphasized the importance of studying interrelationships of climate variation, water variability/distribution and vegetation health (Lu *et al.*, 2000; Fu and Burgher, 2015; Sahu *et al.*, 2024). So far, however, few studies have been conducted in Nigeria which were specifically focused on the vegetation health of streams and the effect of seasonal changes in water availability in stream networks.

The Tangaza region in Sokoto State, Nigeria, is a semi-arid area that is susceptible to climatic variations and human activities that can lead to environmental degradation. Alternating wet and dry seasons are a significant factor in the dynamics of vegetation in the region. The relationships between climate, water resources, population, average of rainfall, and vegetation are important considerations for sustainable land management practices.

The effect of the vegetation changes on the desert encroachment which is considered an environmental problem that has not yet been investigated in Tangaza of Sokoto state of Nigeria which gave rise to the question of the research: How does vegetation dynamics have impact on climatic variability in the study area? Spatial and temporal variations of vegetation in Tangaza are therefore investigated in the dry seasons of 2013 and 2018, and rainy seasons of 2015 and 2016. The combination of the NDVI and stream order

analyses will help to identify the factors that affect the health of the vegetation and to suggest solutions for sustainable management of the ecosystem in the region.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Area

Nigeria has been classified into several vegetation zones as shown in fig. 1. The Sahelian ecological zone in Nigeria covers several states, including Sokoto, Zamfara, Katsina, Jigawa, Yobe, and Borno. Sokoto State, which forms part of this Sahel region, is situated in the northwestern part of Nigeria. It shares international boundaries with the Republic of Niger to the north and is bordered by Katsina State to the east, Niger State to the southeast, Kwara State to the south, and the Republic of Benin to the west. From a geographical perspective, Sokoto State is situated within 10°N and 13°58'N latitude and 4°8'E and 6°54'E longitude, with an area of approximately 62,000 square kilometres (Ekpoh and Nsa, 2011). As far as climate is concerned, the region experiences influences from two main air masses that influence each other; these are the dry tropical continental air mass from the Sahara Desert and the moist tropical maritime air mass from the Atlantic Ocean. The movements of the Inter-Tropical Convergence Zone (ITCZ) determine which of these air masses dominate the region at particular times and hence the distinct wet and dry seasons experienced in the region. Temperatures range between 35°C and 40°C, with highs above 45°C in the months of February to April.

Fig. 1: Ecological Zones of Nigeria

Source: Oluwaseyi, 2017

Tangaza Local Government Area is located on the geographic coordinates of 13°31'N, 4°58'E. This local government area belongs to Sokoto State with a surface area of 2,477 km² and a population of 113,853 in 2006 census data. The boundary of Tangaza Local Government Area lies to the north of the Niger Republic. One of the most remarkable geographical features found in this LGA is Lake Karereyi, which acts as a

seasonal lake that dries up during dry seasons. In Tangaza, there is periodic deposition of sand that destroys vegetation and forms different sand layers.

Fig. 2: Map of Sokoto State, highlighting Tangaza, the study location

Data Requirements and Analyses

This research made use of Landsat data for the years 2013 and 2018 representing the rainy season and dry season, respectively. The selection of 2013 and 2018 was done considering the availability of the data. These represent the average conditions in the wet and dry season. NDVI values were determined using the spectrum bands, and this would help to establish the vegetation health status. Pre-processing procedures were undertaken before using the images to account for radiometric and geometric corrections. Classification was done using varying NDVI zones and their density.

For stream order mapping, SRTM satellite data were employed to establish the Digital Elevation Models. The DEMs were used within a GIS environment to classify the streams into orders based on the Strahler method of classifying streams. These maps were then used to analyze stream orders alongside NDVI maps to understand the relation between vegetation density and stream order/ proximity during both wet and dry seasons.

Table 1: NDVI for 2013 dry and rainy seasons.

ID	NDVI Categories	2013 Dry Season		2013 Rainy Season			
		NDVI	Area (HA)	NDVI	Area (HA)		
1	Sparse	-0.275 - 0.006	328	0%	-0.163 - 0.170	44033	17%
2	Low	0.007- 0.119	76325	30%	0.170 - 0.245	84576	33%
3	Moderate	0.119 - 0.172	140807	55%	0.245 - 0.3199	88859	49%
4	Dense	0.172 - 0.465	37311	15%	0.3199 - 0.569	37303	15%

Table 2: NDVI for 2018 dry and rainy seasons

ID	NDVI categories	2018 2013 Dry season			2018 Rainy season		
		NDVI	Area (HA)		NDVI	Area (HA)	
1	Sparse	NDVI	Area (HA)		NDVI	Area (HA)	
2	Low	-0.219 - 0.095	32144	13%	-0.1463 - 0.173	45311	17%
3	Moderate	0.096 - 0.130	78227	31%	0.174 - 0.238	71073	28%
4	Dense	0.131 - 0.170	126014	49%	0.238- 0.299	92126	36%

The NDVI values analysis of Tangaza and Sokoto State has yielded critical information on the vegetation activities occurring during the dry and rainy seasons of 2013 and 2018, respectively, (tables 1 and 2). The NDVI values were classified into four ranges – sparse, low, moderate, and dense vegetation covers. The distribution as well as the seasonal variation and trends on the 5 years are discussed.

Dry Season Analysis

The amount of area lacking in vegetation (NDVI range -0.275 to 0.006) was very small during the 2013 dry season, accounting for only 328 hectares (<1%). Low vegetation (NDVI 0.007 to 0.119) covered 76,325 hectares (30%), and the largest area (140,807 hectares or 55%) was in the moderate vegetation category (NDVI 0.119 to 0.172), which includes grassland. Dense vegetation (NDVI 0.172 to 0.465) was limited to 37,311 hectares (15%).

The sparse vegetation zone (NDVI -0.219 to 0.095) extended greatly in 2018 to 32,144 ha (13%), which suggests a possible situation of land degradation caused by deforestation, less rain and overgrazing. Low vegetation cover (NDVI 0.096 to 0.130) slightly increased to 78,227 hectares (31%). However, moderate vegetation (NDVI 0.131 to 0.170) decreased to 126,014 hectares (49%), a reduction of 14,793 ha from 2013, and dense vegetation (NDVI 0.171 to 0.462) contracted to 18,386 hectares. The changes indicate reduction in vegetation density possibly because of anthropogenic activities like the encroachment of agricultural land and the collection of fuel wood, or climatic changes like rainfall deficiency.

Rainy Season Analysis

During the 2013 rainy season, sparse vegetation (NDVI -0.163 to 0.170) covered 44,033 hectares (17%). Low vegetation (NDVI 0.170 to 0.245) covered to 84,576 hectares (33%). Moderate vegetation (NDVI 0.245 to 0.3199) dominated (49%, 88,859 hectares) while dense vegetation (NDVI 0.3199 to 0.569) covered 37,303 hectares (15%) primarily in close proximity to the streams or cultivated areas. In 2018, sparse vegetation (NDVI -0.1463 to 0.173) slightly increased to 45,311 hectares (17%). The area with low vegetation (NDVI 0.174 to 0.238) decreased to 71,073 hectares (28%), a reduction of 13,503 ha compared to 2013, while moderate vegetation (NDVI 0.238 to 0.299) rose to 92,126 hectares (36%). Specifically, dense vegetation (NDVI 0.299 to 0.511) grew to 48,230 ha, representing an increase of 19%, corresponding to better vegetation growth in the rainy season, which may be attributed to more precipitation or vegetation recovery.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Seasonal variations indicate the higher NDVI values in rainy seasons which are associated with increased vegetation growth with more rainfall (Fu and Burgher, 2015). When looking at 2013 and 2018, however, vegetation density was lower during the dry season, particularly in areas where there was initially dense vegetation (tables 1 and 2). The trends reflect the impact of anthropogenic and environmental factors such as deforestation, extent of agriculture and climate variability on vegetation health (Olaniyi *et al.*, 2013; Ibrahim *et al.*, 2017; Agbaje *et al.*, 2020) particularly overgrazing and extraction of fuel wood in the study area.

Fig. 3: Map showing the relationship between stream order and 2013 rainy season

Fig. 4: Map showing the relationship between stream order and 2013 dry season

Fig. 5: Map showing the relationship between stream order and 2018 rainy season

Fig. 6: Map showing the relationship between stream order and 2018 dry season.

The NDVI analysis for Tangaza shows the complex interaction between climatic conditions, hydrological characteristics and plant dynamics, with the vegetation responding to precipitation. During the 2013 dry season, the highest vegetation density (based on NDVI) was observed on moderate vegetation density areas (140,807 hectares), while the least vegetation density was found in sparse vegetation areas (328 hectares) as shown in table 1. In 2018, there was a reduction in the dense vegetation and an increasing in the sparse

ones, indicating the degradation of land (tables 1 and 2). In contrast, we observed more vegetation health during the rainy seasons, especially associated with higher order streams, highlighting the need for water availability for vegetation growth.

The association between stream order derived from SRTM data and NDVI for dry and rainy seasons underlines the spatial relationship between stream order and vegetation patterns. Rainy season NDVI values are higher over areas where the stream order is higher, reflecting increased vegetation health in these areas because of the water supply (Fu and Burgher, 2015, supports stream-vegetation relationships). In contrast, the lowest NDVI scores occur in all stream orders during the dry season, reflecting lower vegetation cover. Lower stream orders (usually small stream and tributaries) tend to have lower NDVI values, especially in spring, indicating little influence of water on vegetation growth. But the areas close to the higher order streams are found to have dense vegetation (NDVI>0.30) in rainy period highlighting the importance of higher order streams in supporting vegetation growth. These decreases in NDVI values throughout the dry season, even in the vicinity of higher order streams, indicate the seasonality of vegetation's reliance on stream water resources and precipitation.

This analysis shows that stream order may provide useful information for detecting potential vegetation health and distribution, particularly in conjunction with NDVI assessment. This was also confirmed by Sahu *et al.* (2024). It was concluded that there is very significant relationship between the hydrological features and the vegetation dynamics especially in Tangaza (semi-arid environment) in relation to both the quantity and the quality of plants. The changes observed indicate the importance of sustainable land use practices to reduce vegetation loss and improve the resilience of ecosystems, including afforestation initiatives and managing grazing practices. Vegetation change monitoring, based on remote sensing, such as NDVI, can provide valuable information that contributes to policy decision making (Jensen, 2015).

The results are complemented by the stream order analysis. Vegetation was found to be dense along higher order streams during the rainy season, and consistently lower NDVI was recorded along lower order streams. This pattern shows how vegetation health is related to water access, especially in areas where water is scarce, such as Tangaza. The seasonal fluctuation in NDVI is also an indicator of the sensitivity of the vegetation to the climatic changes, and the movement of the ITCZ is a key factor in producing these fluctuations. These effects are further compounded by anthropogenic activity including deforestation and over-cultivation leading to further degradation of land and loss of ecological productivity.

CONCLUSION

This study highlights the importance of hydrological and climatic variables in the pattern of vegetation in Sokoto State with Tangaza as a case study. The rainy seasons are associated with enhanced vegetation growth, and dry seasons are associated with greater areas at risk for land degradation, as shown by NDVI and stream order analyses. The results highlight the need for sustainable land management, and specific policy measures to reduce vegetation degradation and increase ecosystem resilience. Leveraging remote sensing tools like NDVI for monitoring can provide actionable insights to support these efforts and inform adaptive strategies to address climatic variability in semi-arid regions which may include implementation

of sustainable land management practices, water resources management, reforestation programs, community awareness and involvement, policy and regulation, and further research, particularly in these arid and semi-arid zones. This study will be helpful in the management of semi-arid ecosystems, but more rigorous statistical analysis like correlation studies to determine empirical relationships between hydrological parameters (stream orders) and vegetation dynamics needs to be conducted in further studies. In addition, measures for the validation of NDVI values should be incorporated into future studies, and longer temporal datasets used in order to identify long-term trends, which was not done in this study.

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